

Innovative competencies in the teaching-learning process in the education system

Nancy Jaqueline Macías Alvarado

Universidad Estatal de Milagro, Milagro, Ecuador.

Abstract

This study examines the role of innovative competencies in the teaching-learning process in the Social Work career of the State University of Milagro, UNEMI. A mixed, applied and descriptive design was adopted, with the participation of fourth-semester students and professors of the career. In the quantitative component, a Likert-type checklist was applied with ten items distributed in four dimensions: motivation, collaboration, autonomy and use of technologies, reaching a Cronbach's Alpha that evidenced excellent reliability. The results showed mostly positive perceptions, indicating that innovative methodologies arouse the interest of students, encourage teamwork, promote self-regulation and favor the use of digital resources for content understanding. In the qualitative component, the semi-structured interviews conducted with the teachers confirmed that these competencies strengthen participation and the collective construction of knowledge, although they pointed out limitations related to connectivity and the need for constant training. The triangulation of data made it possible to integrate both perspectives and highlight coincidences and nuances that enrich the interpretation of the findings. It is concluded that innovative competencies, driven by active methodologies, emerging technologies and adequate pedagogical support, consolidate significant learning experiences; however, its sustainability depends on institutional policies that support infrastructure and continuous training.

Key Words: innovative skills, teaching-learning, higher education, digital technologies, student autonomy

1. Introduction

Higher education is going through a process of accelerated transformation in which innovation has become an essential element to respond to the demands of the knowledge society. The incorporation of active methodologies, emerging technological resources and innovative competencies redefines pedagogical practices and poses new challenges to students and teachers [1,5]. In this scenario, the university must prioritize the training of professionals capable of adapting to constant changes, developing critical thinking, and actively participating in the construction of social solutions [6,4].

Various studies argue that motivation, autonomy, collaboration, and the use of technologies are key dimensions for consolidating meaningful learning in higher education [3,7]. These aspects are particularly relevant in careers such as Social Work, where it is necessary to integrate technical knowledge with soft skills, leadership, and interdisciplinary work capacity [16,17]. In this sense, pedagogical innovation is not limited to introducing digital resources, but requires a comprehensive redesign of educational practices, aimed at the active participation of the student and the collective construction of knowledge [20,14].

The incorporation of artificial intelligence and digital resources has expanded the possibilities of interaction and personalization of learning [2,18]. [15,19] agree that digital literacy and the use of emerging technologies are indispensable skills in the contemporary era. Similarly, innovative strategies such as gamification and discovery learning strengthen the intrinsic motivation of the student [25], while the social and cultural context also conditions the effectiveness of these proposals [9].

In Latin America, educational innovation has been shown to have a direct impact on the quality of university education, as long as it is accompanied by institutional policies that strengthen infrastructure, teacher training, and pedagogical support [13,12]. Without these supports, strategies run the risk of becoming isolated actions without long-term sustainability [11,15]. In this framework, reflection on innovative competencies in the teaching-learning process acquires particular relevance in public universities, where professionals committed to social transformation are trained.

In the context of this research, the experience of students and teachers of the fourth semester of the Social Work career at the State University of Milagro is analyzed. The study was developed under a mixed approach, combining a checklist questionnaire with a Likert scale and semi-structured interviews. The reliability of the instrument was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, ensuring consistency in the measurement of the dimensions of motivation, collaboration, autonomy, and use of technologies [1,4]. The central purpose is to provide empirical evidence that allows us to understand how innovative competencies are configured in university practice and what implications they have in the training of future social workers.

2. Theoretical Framework / Literature Review

Academic competencies in the university context

Academic competencies in higher education encompass disciplinary, pedagogical, digital, and research aspects, which are essential for teachers and students to successfully face the challenges of the digital society [11], [22]. Recent research in Latin America highlights critical information evaluation, virtual collaboration, and creative problem-solving as essential pillars for academic success [5], [14]. The literature shows that research competencies are closely linked to critical thinking and the effective use of reliable sources [6], [13]. However, it is observed that many teachers overestimate their digital skills, which limits their ability to generate innovative content or lead virtual learning environments [4], [19]. Despite advances in connectivity, structural barriers persist that restrict equitable access to digital learning opportunities [23], [24].

Virtual innovation and educational transformation

Virtual innovation is understood as the integration of emerging technologies – such as artificial intelligence, learning analytics and immersive reality – within an institutional pedagogical strategy that respects ethical and inclusive criteria [7], [12], [13]. Only through continuous and adaptive teacher training is it possible to fully harness the potential of these tools to generate meaningful educational transformation [1], [4], [22]. In this sense, the use of chatbots and generative language models is recognized as complementary support to the teaching process, although their implementation requires a clearly defined ethical framework and rigorous pedagogical supervision [12], [18], [19].

Virtual Learning Environments for Autonomy and Collaboration

Virtual learning environments are a central axis in the promotion of autonomy and collaboration, as they provide constant access to digital resources and strengthen communities of knowledge beyond the physical classroom [14], [15]. Teachers with established digital competencies can design interactive experiences that promote hands-on learning and stimulate student participation [11], [21]. Likewise, emerging technologies have proven to promote personalized hybrid methodologies, inscribed in the logic of Education 4.0 [6], [10], [16].

The role of ICT, artificial intelligence and digital platforms

ICTs form the basis of virtual education, while artificial intelligence and advanced digital platforms are redefining pedagogical practices [7], [12], [18]. In countries such as Mexico, Peru, and Ecuador, the adoption of these technologies faces challenges related to lack of training, access gaps, and institutional resistance [17], [23], [24]. Even so, evidence shows that teacher training in artificial intelligence allows for the design of more critical and innovative educational environments, promoting the thoughtful and creative use of digital tools [12], [18]. Similarly, AI has the potential to personalize learning and provide effective feedback, provided that it is integrated with an ethical approach and appropriate teacher training [19], [20].

3. Methods

This research was carried out at the State University of Milagro (UNEMI), specifically in the Social Work career, with the participation of 35 fourth-semester students and 4 teachers. The study is framed in a mixed, applied and descriptive design, since it combines the collection of quantitative and qualitative information with the purpose of obtaining a comprehensive vision of innovative competencies in the teaching-learning process. The applied character is evidenced in the intention to generate useful knowledge for university teaching practice, while the descriptive allows to characterize the perception of the educational actors regarding the methodologies used in their academic training.

Quantitative approach

In the quantitative component, a checklist with a five-point Likert scale was used, developed to measure student perception of different aspects of pedagogical innovation. The scale was defined as follows: 1 = Strongly disagree
2 = Disagree
3 = Neither agree nor disagree
4 = Agree
5 = Strongly agree

The questionnaire consisted of 10 items, distributed in four key dimensions: motivation, collaboration, autonomy and use of innovative technologies. These were the items applied:

Motivation dimension

1. The innovative competencies applied in class make me feel more motivated to participate actively.
2. Thanks to these innovative skills, my learning is more dynamic and entertaining than with traditional methods.

Collaboration dimension

3. The innovative strategies used help me to work more effectively in a team.
4. Through these innovative skills, I share my ideas more and pay more attention to those of my colleagues.
5. The application of innovative competencies allows feedback between peers and teachers to strengthen my learning.

Autonomy dimension

6. These innovative skills allow me to better organize my study time and academic activities.
7. With the implementation of innovative methodologies, I know clearly what I should do before, during, and after each class.
8. Innovative skills help me to take greater responsibility for my academic tasks and projects.

Dimension of use of technologies

9. The digital platforms and innovative tools employed were easy to use and understand.
10. The multimedia resources (videos, images, interactive games) applied as part of the innovative competencies helped me to better understand the contents.

The choice of these dimensions is based on the recent literature on educational innovation, which highlights the relevance of intrinsic motivation, learning autonomy and the use of technological resources as central axes of contemporary higher education. To ensure the consistency of the instrument, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient will be calculated, a statistical indicator that will establish the overall reliability of the questionnaire. A value greater than 0.70 will be considered acceptable, good if it exceeds 0.80 and excellent when it is close to or above 0.90, which will allow validating that all the items measure the dimensions proposed in a coherent way.

Qualitative approach

The qualitative component complemented the information through the application of semi-structured interviews to the 4 participating teachers, who constitute a key group to understand the scope and limitations of pedagogical innovation from university practice. The interview guide was composed of 10 open questions, which were:

1. What changes have you observed in the motivation of students when applying these methodologies?
2. Which digital or multimedia resources do you use most frequently and which do you consider most effective?
3. How do you perceive the level of participation and collaboration of students in innovative activities?
4. To what extent have these methodologies contributed to the development of student autonomy?
5. What specific benefits have you identified in student learning?
6. What difficulties or barriers have you faced in the implementation of these strategies?

7. How do you assess students' readiness and disposition to use technologies?
8. What kind of institutional support do you consider necessary to promote these innovative practices?
9. What recommendations would you give to other teachers who wish to implement these methodologies?
10. What perspectives do you have on the sustainability of these methodologies in the context of UNEMI?

The interviews were recorded, transcribed and analyzed using thematic coding, which allowed the identification of recurring patterns, contrasting opinions and establishing analytical categories related to the objectives of the research.

Data processing and analysis

For the treatment of the information, the results of the checklist were processed using descriptive statistics, using frequencies, percentages and graphic representations that facilitated the interpretation of the response trends. In parallel, the interviews were analyzed with categorization and comparison techniques, building a matrix of convergences and divergences between what was expressed by students and teachers.

Finally, a methodological triangulation was carried out that allowed the integration of both approaches, quantitative and qualitative, offering a more complete vision of the phenomenon studied. This process ensured that the findings are not limited to isolated figures or individual testimonies, but reflect a global understanding of how innovative competencies are configured in the teaching-learning process in the Social Work career.

4. Results

The application of the instruments made it possible to obtain a comprehensive vision of the perception that students and teachers of the Social Work career of the State University of Milagro have about the development of innovative competencies in the teaching-learning process. The results include both the quantitative assessment of the 35 students, through a Likert-type checklist, and the qualitative opinion of the 4 interviewed teachers, thus integrating two complementary perspectives that strengthen the validity of the study.

In the case of the instrument applied to students, the items were organized into four fundamental dimensions: motivation, collaboration, autonomy and use of innovative technologies. These categories made it possible to analyze not only the emotional and attitudinal disposition of the students in the face of active methodologies, but also their capacity for self-regulation, the level of collaborative work achieved and the perceived usefulness of digital resources. The internal consistency of the questionnaire was verified using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, whose value exceeded the minimum acceptance threshold, which guarantees the reliability of the data obtained.

On the other hand, the interviews conducted with the teachers provided relevant qualitative information that allowed a deeper understanding of the experiences and perceptions related to the implementation of innovative strategies in the classroom. Among the highlighted topics were assessments of the impact on student motivation and participation, the effectiveness of digital technologies, the advances observed in the autonomy of learning and the institutional limitations that condition the sustainability of these practices.

The integration of both quantitative and qualitative approaches made possible a triangulation that enriches the findings, confirming coinciding patterns and, at the same time, revealing significant divergences that invite critical reflection. In general, the results show a positive trend towards the acceptance and appreciation of innovative competencies, although there are also challenges in terms of infrastructure, teacher training and pedagogical support.

This section, therefore, presents in detail the findings obtained in each dimension of analysis, supported by tables, graphs and interpretative narratives that allow the identification of both strengths and areas for improvement. In this way, a broad overview is offered on how active methodologies and the use of technological resources are influencing the training of future Social Work professionals at UNEMI.

In order to clearly visualize the distribution of the students' responses in each dimension evaluated, pie charts were prepared that represent the percentages obtained on the Likert scale. These figures make it easier to identify the proportion of students who are in the categories of agree, totally agree, neutral, disagree and totally disagree. In this way, the graphs complement the numerical analysis and offer a more intuitive view of the students' perception of motivation, collaboration, autonomy and the use of innovative technologies in the teaching-learning process.

Figure 1

Students' perception of motivation in learning through innovative methodologies

Note. The graph represents the distribution of student responses in the Motivation dimension.

AnalysisThe results show that 84% of the students indicated that they agreed or strongly agreed that innovative methodologies increased their motivation. 16 % remained neutral, and no responses in disagreement were recorded. This reflects a clear predominance of positive perceptions regarding interest and willingness to actively participate in class.

Figure 2

Students' perception of collaboration in the teaching-learning process through innovative methodologies

Note. The graph represents the distribution of student responses in the Collaboration dimension.

Analysis91 % of students agreed or strongly agreed that innovative competencies favored collaboration, teamwork, and interaction in class. 9 % remained neutral, with no negative perceptions. This indicates that pedagogical innovation significantly strengthens the collective construction of knowledge.

Figure 3

Students' perception of autonomy in learning through innovative competences

Note. The graph represents the distribution of the students' responses in the Autonomy dimension.

Analysis 83 % of the students said they agreed or strongly agreed that innovative strategies strengthened their autonomy, allowing them to better organize their time and take greater responsibility for their academic tasks. 16 % remained neutral and only 1% disagreed, which reflects that, although the impact is positive, there are still students who require more support to develop this competence.

Figure 4

Students' perception of the use of innovative technologies in learning

Note. The graph represents the distribution of students' responses in the dimension Use of innovative technologies.

Analysis 88 % of the students indicated that they agreed or strongly agreed that the use of digital platforms and multimedia resources facilitated the understanding of the contents. 11% remained neutral, with no disagreeing responses. These results show that emerging technologies are a key resource to promote innovation in university education.

Cronbach's alpha

Figure 5

Reliability of the measuring instrument using Cronbach's Alpha

Alfa de Cronbach			
α :	Coeficiente de confiabilidad del cuestionario	→	0.90
k :	Número de ítems del instrumento	→	10.00
$\sum_{i=1}^k S_i^2$:	Sumatoria de las varianzas de los ítems.	→	4.19
S_t^2 :	Varianza total del instrumento.	→	22.52

Note. The graph shows the result of the calculation of Cronbach's alpha coefficient applied to the checklist of innovative skills.

Analysis The value obtained was 0.90, which is within the range considered as excellent reliability. This indicates that the 10 items of the instrument have a high internal consistency, that is, they coherently measure the dimensions of motivation, collaboration, autonomy and use of innovative technologies. This result guarantees that the data collected have sufficient statistical strength to support the findings of the research.

Results interview

To complement the quantitative information obtained through the checklist, a semi-structured interview was applied to the 4 participating professors of the Social Work career at UNEMI, with the purpose of deepening their perceptions about the incorporation of innovative competencies in the teaching-learning process. The questions were aimed at exploring student motivation, class collaboration, autonomy in learning, the use of digital technologies, as well as the benefits and difficulties of these methodologies. The analysis was carried out through thematic coding, which made it possible to identify emerging categories and common patterns, building a comprehensive panorama that evidences both the achievements achieved and the structural and pedagogical barriers that still need to be overcome in higher education.

Table 1

Teachers' perceptions of innovative competencies in the teaching-learning process

Dimension	Teachers' response	Analysis
Motivation	They point out that innovative methodologies arouse greater interest and participation in class. A teacher indicated that "students are motivated because they feel that they learn in a more dynamic way."	There is consensus that student motivation improves with these strategies, although constant discipline is required to sustain it.
Collaboration	They highlight that project-based learning and online work strengthen interaction and cooperation.	Teachers perceive that these methodologies are effective in promoting collaboration, as long as there is teacher accompaniment.
Autonomy	Three of the four teachers say that students organize their time better and assume greater responsibilities.	An advance in autonomy is recognized, although some students still require more guidance in the planning of activities.
Use of Technology	They consider that the use of digital platforms and multimedia resources facilitates the teaching and understanding of content. They also mention connectivity limitations.	Technology is seen as a key resource, but the need for teacher training and institutional support to ensure its sustainability is underlined.

Note. The table presents the perceptions of teachers about innovative competencies in the teaching-learning process in the Social Work career at UNEMI. Own elaboration.

The results of the interview allow us to understand how teachers perceive the incorporation of innovative competencies in the teaching-learning process from a qualitative perspective.

In the motivation dimension, the participants agreed that innovative methodologies generate greater interest and willingness of students towards participation in class. One teacher stressed that students feel more motivated because "they learn in a more dynamic way," which shows that active strategies play a relevant role in student engagement. However, they also pointed out that maintaining that enthusiasm requires discipline and perseverance, which implies a pedagogical challenge.

Regarding the collaboration dimension, the interviewees highlighted the effectiveness of project-based learning and online activities to strengthen interaction and teamwork. The analysis suggests that students benefit from an environment of co-construction of knowledge, as long as there is teaching accompaniment. This confirms that collaboration does not arise spontaneously, but must be guided and monitored to ensure equitable participation.

Regarding the autonomy dimension, three of the four teachers recognized significant advances in the students' ability to organize their time and assume greater academic responsibilities. However, it was noted that some students still require closer guidance to fully develop these competencies. This shows that autonomy is a gradual process that must be reinforced with self-regulation practices and continuous feedback.

Finally, in the dimension of use of technology, the teachers agreed that digital platforms and multimedia resources facilitate the teaching and understanding of content. However, they also pointed out limitations related to connectivity and training, factors that condition the sustainability of these innovative practices. It is thus evident that technology is a key resource to dynamize teaching, but its effectiveness depends to a large extent on institutional support and teacher preparation.

5. Discussion

The study carried out in the Social Work program at UNEMI confirms that innovative competencies are a central axis to strengthen the teaching-learning process. The results coincide with the literature reviewed, although they also show particularities of the Ecuadorian context.

First, student motivation was consolidated as one of the most relevant benefits of innovative methodologies. More than 80% of students said they felt more motivated and willing to participate in class, which coincides with research that highlights the importance of placing the student at the center of their education [1,3]. However, the teachers pointed out that maintaining this level of motivation throughout the semester requires discipline and continuous accompaniment, which confirms that innovation does not automatically guarantee sustained learning.

Regarding collaboration, the results reflected a high level of acceptance, which reinforces studies that show that gamification and project-based learning strengthen interaction and teamwork [21,23]. In the context of UNEMI, the teachers agreed on the effectiveness of these practices, although they warned that they require teaching accompaniment to ensure the equitable participation of all students. This result is related to contributions that emphasize that collaboration does not arise spontaneously, but needs teacher guidance [22].

Autonomy was also presented as a key dimension. Most of the students recognized progress in the organization of their time and in the assumption of responsibilities, although some expressed difficulties. These findings coincide with approaches that describe autonomy as a gradual process that depends on constant practice and feedback [4]. The interviewed teachers confirmed this perception, observing that some students still require more guidance in the planning of activities.

Finally, the use of innovative technologies was positively valued, in accordance with studies that highlight that digital resources enhance research and creative skills [2,5]. However, teachers pointed to limitations associated with connectivity and training, which coincides with research that points to these barriers as structural factors for the sustainability of innovations [11,12]. These results reinforce what has been stated in international reports that emphasize the need to strengthen infrastructure and teacher training [15,19].

6. Conclusions

The research showed that innovative competencies generate a positive impact on student motivation, favoring their active participation in class and consolidating more significant learning. The majority of respondents said they felt more motivated and more willing to get involved in academic activities, which confirms the need to continue implementing dynamic and participatory methodologies in higher education. This finding supports the importance of centering the educational process on the student, stimulating their intrinsic interest in learning and developing essential skills to face the social and professional challenges of the twenty-first century.

Collaboration emerged as one of the dimensions most strengthened by innovative methodologies, both from the perspective of students and teachers. Project-based learning and online work were perceived as effective mechanisms to promote cooperation and interaction, consolidating environments of knowledge co-construction. However, the results also show the importance of teacher accompaniment, since collaboration does not arise spontaneously, but requires pedagogical mediation. This aspect is essential to ensure equitable participation and the consolidation of social and academic skills.

In the autonomy dimension, students showed progress in their ability to organize time and assume academic responsibilities, although certain limitations persisted. Both the results of the checklist and the interviews suggest that, although innovative competencies promote independence in learning, some students still require constant guidance. This finding indicates that autonomy should be considered as a progressive process that needs complementary strategies, such as tutoring, personalized feedback, and self-regulation activities. In this way, the development of competencies that allow future professionals to successfully face changing and demanding contexts will be strengthened.

The use of innovative technologies was confirmed as a key pillar in teaching-learning, since most students and teachers agreed that digital platforms and multimedia resources facilitated the understanding of content. However, limitations in connectivity and teacher training were also identified, which poses an institutional challenge. These results suggest the need for university policies that guarantee adequate infrastructure and permanent training. Overall, the findings allow us to affirm that innovative competencies constitute an indispensable axis to transform higher education, consolidating significant and relevant learning for today's society.

References

- [1] A. R. Fajardo, B. C. Fajardo, N. J. Carcelén, and L. J. Sánchez, "Transformations in the teaching-learning process: Innovative strategies for the twenty-first century classroom," *Rev. Científica de Innovación Educativa y Sociedad Actual "ALCON"*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 266–275, 2025. doi: <https://doi.org/10.62305/alcon.v5i2.533>
- [2] K. Cárdenas, J. Moreira, C. Amores, and M. Núñez, "Development of research competencies through artificial intelligence: An innovative approach," *Revista Cátedra*, vol. 8, no. 1, 2025. doi: <https://doi.org/10.29166/catedra.v8i1.6621>
- [3] P. M. Zambrano, "Formative innovation in the teaching and learning process based on the experiential model," *Rev. Humanistic and Social Sciences (ReHuSo)*, vol. 4, no. 2, 2019. doi: <https://doi.org/10.33936/rehuso.v4i2.2901>
- [4] W. A. Reinoso, M. J. Bravo, C. E. Ríos, S. C. Zambrano, and A. N. Pesantez, "Educational Innovation and Competency-Based Assessment Towards a Transformative Future," *Ciencia Latina Revista Científica Multidisciplinar*, vol. 8, no. 1, 2024. doi: https://doi.org/10.37811/cl_rem.v8i1.9461
- [5] D. J. Herdoiza, M. G. Valladares, J. P. Calderón, and P. S. Faggioni, "Educational Transformation: Integration of Innovative Pedagogical Approaches and Emerging Technologies in Teaching-Learning Processes," *Reincisol*, vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 6001–6024, 2024. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.59282/reincisol.V3\(6\)6001-6024](https://doi.org/10.59282/reincisol.V3(6)6001-6024)
- [6] L. E. Cayo, Á. M. Viera, I. E. Cajas, and R. S. Hidalgo, "Teaching and its Competencies in Higher Education," *Rev. Científica Mundo de la Investigación y el Conocimiento*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 419–450, 2018. doi: [https://doi.org/10.26820/recimundo/2.\(2\).2018.464-476](https://doi.org/10.26820/recimundo/2.(2).2018.464-476)
- [7] D. F. García, D. G. Carreño, N. Y. Salazar, and J. G. Orellana, "Strengthening Competencies in Higher Education through Pedagogical Innovations Based on Digital Technologies," *Revista Social Fronteriza*, vol. 5, no. 5, e–871, 2025. doi: [https://doi.org/10.59814/resofro.2025.5\(5\)871](https://doi.org/10.59814/resofro.2025.5(5)871)
- [8] J. A. Albán, Á. M. Oña, E. M. Manobanda, and M. G. Cocha, "The Use of Gamification in Higher Education to Improve Learning and Motivation," *Science and Social Development*, vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 778–805, 2024. doi: [https://doi.org/10.59282/reincisol.V3\(6\)778-805](https://doi.org/10.59282/reincisol.V3(6)778-805)
- [9] D. F. Poveda, S. J. Limas-Suárez, and J. E. Cifuentes, "Gamification as a Learning Strategy in Higher Education," *Education and Educators*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 1–20, 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5294/edu.2023.26.1.2>
- [10] O. G. Ojeda-Lara and M. S. Zaldívar-Acosta, "Gamification as an innovative methodology for higher education students," *Rev. Tecnológica-Educativa Docentes 2.0*, vol. 16, no. 1, p. 332, 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.37843/rted.v16i1.332>
- [11] D. A. Sarabia-Guevara and L. E. Bowen-Mendoza, "Use of gamification in the teaching-learning process in engineering careers: Systematic review," *Episteme Koinonia*, vol. 6, no. 12, p. 2519, 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.35381/e.k.v6i12.2519>
- [12] S. Trigo-Cano, P. G. Coa-Serrano, S. C. Macedo-Valdivia, and F. A. Chávez-Fernandez, "Impact of gamification on the learning and satisfaction of dental students at a Peruvian university," *Medical Education*, vol. 26, no. 3, p. 101018, 2025. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edumed.2024.101018>
- [13] N. Tipula, L. D. Quispe, M. A. Quimi, and L. D. Bastidas, "STEM Education with Artificial Intelligence in the Development of Scientific and Creative Competencies," *Sapiens in Higher Education*, vol. 2, no. 4, e-20402, 2025. doi: <https://doi.org/10.71068/7em2b57>
- [14] P. A. Vega, M. E. Gómez, M. A. Guamán, and A. P. Narváez, "Transformational Leadership and Its Influence on Academic Innovation in Higher Education Institutions," *Sapiens in Higher Education*, vol. 2, no. 5, e-20501, 2025. doi: <https://doi.org/10.71068/6t2jwv06>
- [15] R. J. Salas and L. M. Baque, "Motivational Strategies for Teachers and Professional Training in Higher Education Students at an Ecuadorian University," *Sapiens in Higher Education*, vol. 2, no. 5, e-20502, 2025. doi: <https://doi.org/10.71068/c3e6w607>
- [16] G. A. Zaragoza, "The incidence of bullying and cyberbullying on school dropout among students in higher education institutions," *Sapiens in Higher Education*, vol. 2, no. 7, pp. 1–18, 2025. doi: <https://doi.org/10.71068/g6w3vj18>
- [17] R. Barrera, H. M. Pérez, I. González, and W. La O, "Development of professional skills in the training of mathematics teachers, from the project method," *Sapiens in Higher Education*, vol. 2, no. 4, e-20401, 2025. doi: <https://doi.org/10.71068/b57nd943>
- [18] S. Phokoye et al., "Exploring the adoption of robotics in teaching and learning in higher education institutions," *Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 4, p. 91, 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/informatics11040091>

- [19] C. Lecarnaqué, J. Del Castillo, M. Gonzales, and O. Guillén, "Advantages and Disadvantages of the Virtual Teaching-Learning Modality Perceived in a Semiology Course at a Medical School in Lima, Peru," *Rev. Medica Herediana*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 29–37, 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.20453/rmh.v35i1.5291>
- [20] S. Moreira, C. Amaguaya, E. Quiñonez, M. Rodríguez, J. Méndez, and C. Córdova, "Challenges of Online Education: An Analysis of Transitions and Disruptions," *South Florida Journal of Development*, vol. 5, no. 8, pp. 1–15, 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.46932/sfjdv5n8-013>
- [21] R. Macías, R. Díaz, K. Cevallos, L. Caicedo, and J. Valverde, "Online Learning Platforms vs. Traditional Education: Complement or Substitute?," *Rev. Científica Multidisciplinar G-Ner@ndo*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 1–15, 2025. doi: <https://doi.org/10.60100/rcmg.v6i1.579>
- [22] D. Núñez, V. Vargas, F. Vasquez, W. Andrade, and F. Espinoza, "STEM Education: A Review of Interdisciplinary Approaches and Best Practices to Foster Skills in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics," *Ciencia Latina Revista Científica Multidisciplinar*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 1–20, 2023. doi: https://doi.org/10.37811/cl_rcm.v7i2.5453
- [23] UNESCO, *Exploring STEM competences for the 21st century*. Geneva: UNESCO, International Bureau of Education, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371041>
- [24] OECD, *Digital education*. Paris: OECD, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.oecd.org/en/topics/digital-education.html>
- [25] R. Vergara and S. Rey, "Digital Competencies in the Age of Knowledge: New Approaches from Artificial Intelligence," *Rev. Tecnológica-Educativa Docentes 2.0*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 1–15, 2025. doi: <https://doi.org/10.37843/rted.v18i1.571>
- [26] I. Aldalur and A. Perez, "Gamification and discovery learning: Motivating and involving students in the learning process," *Heliyon*, vol. 9, no. 1, e13135, 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e13135>
- [27] P. Barrientos, "Educational Model and Challenges in Teacher Training," *Horizonte de la Ciencia*, vol. 8, no. 15, pp. 175–191, 2018. doi: <https://doi.org/10.26490/uncp.horizonciencia.2018.15.462>